

Nucleons On Demand

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The electrical signature of Nucleons (Proton/Neutron pairs) is the simple charge vector

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Nucleon pairs are designed here using the mechanism in [1]: 6 x 6 content matrices C such that

$$C \begin{pmatrix} q(u) \\ q(d) \\ q(c) \\ q(s) \\ q(t) \\ q(b) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

drawing from all six Quarks: Up(**u**), Down (**d**), Charm(**c**), Strange (**s**), Top(**t**) and Bottom(**b**). Fractional charges are replaced with their signs; thus

	u	d	c	s	t	b
q(old)	2/3	-1/3	2/3	-1/3	2/3	-1/3
q(new)	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1

As a crosscheck - though not really necessary

$$\begin{pmatrix} q(u) \\ q(d) \\ q(c) \\ q(s) \\ q(t) \\ q(b) \end{pmatrix} = \text{Inv}(C) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Content matrices are shown below inside color-coded tables; Nucleon sets are in the last column in yellow, all satisfying the electrical charge property.

For combinatorial sanity, exemplars are restricted to two per case; and Anti-particles - though would certainly fit here - have been excluded from the mix. Each case will show 2, or 3, ..., or (sic) 6 entries in each row.

Case 2.

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$	2	1					uud
$N2^0$	2	2					uudd
$N3^1$			2	1			ccs
$N4^0$			2	2			ccss
$N5^1$					2	1	ttb
$N6^0$					2	2	ttbb

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$	2			1			uus
$N2^0$	2			2			uuss
$N3^1$			2			1	ccb
$N4^0$			2			2	ccbb
$N5^1$		1			2		dtb
$N6^0$		2			2		ddtb

Case 3.

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$		1	1		1		dct
$N2^0$	1	2	1				uddc
$N3^1$	1	1			1		udt
$N4^0$				1	2	1	sttb
$N5^1$			1	1	1		cst
$N6^0$			1		1	2	ctbb

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$			1		1	1	ctb
$N2^0$	1	2			1		uddt
$N3^1$	1		1	1			ucs
$N4^0$			2	1		1	ccsb
$N5^1$	1		1			1	ucb
$N6^0$	1				1	2	utbb

Case 4.

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$	2	1	1	1			uudcs
$N2^0$		1	1	1	1		dcst
$N3^1$	2			1	1	1	uustb
$N4^0$	1	1	1			1	udcb
$N5^1$			1	1	2	1	cstb
$N6^0$	1			1	1	1	ustb

	u	d	c	s	t	b	
$N1^1$	2	1			1	1	uudtb
$N2^0$	1			1	1	1	ustb
$N3^1$	1	1			2	1	udttb
$N4^0$	1	1	1	1			udcs
$N5^1$		1	1		2	1	dcttb
$N6^0$	1	1			1	1	udtb

Case 5.

	u	d	c	s	t	b		u	d	c	s	t	b	
N1¹	1	1	1		1	1	udctb	N1¹	2	1	1	2	1	uudcsst
N2⁰		1	2	1	1	1	dccstb	N2⁰	2	1		1	1	uudstb
N3¹	1	1	1	1	1		udcst	N3¹	2	1	2	1		uudccsb
N4⁰	1		1	1	1	2	ucstbb	N4⁰	1	2	1		1	uddctb
N5¹	2	1	1		1	2	uudctbb	N5¹	1		1	1	1	ucstb
N6⁰	1	1	1	2	1		udcsst	N6⁰	1	1		1	2	udsttb

Case 6.

	u	d	c	s	t	b		u	d	c	s	t	b	
N1¹	2	1	1	1	1	1	uudcstb	N1¹	1	1	1	1	2	udcsttb
N2⁰	1	1	1	1	1	1	udcstb	N2⁰	2	1	1	2	1	uudcsstb
N3¹	1	1	2	1	1	1	udccstb	N3¹	2	2	1	1	2	uuddcsttb
N4⁰	2	1	1	1	1	2	uudcstbb	N4⁰	1	1	1	2	2	udcssttb
N5¹	1	1	1	1	2	1	udcsttb	N5¹	2	1	2	2	1	uudccsstb
N6⁰	1	1	2	2	1	1	udccsstb	N6⁰	2	2	1	1	1	uuddcstb

Derived Nucleons are tabled below for convenience; all are actually unique!

	Case2	Case2	Case3	Case3	Case4	Case4	Case5	Case5	Case6	Case6
N1¹	uud	uus	dct	ctb	uudcs	uudtb	udctb	uudcsst	uudcstb	udcsttb
N2⁰	uudd	uuss	uddc	uddt	dcst	ustb	dccstb	uudstb	udcstb	uudcsstb
N3¹	ccs	ccb	udt	ucs	uustb	udttb	udcst	uudccsb	udccstb	uuddcsttb
N4⁰	ccss	ccbb	sttb	ccsb	udcb	udcs	ucstbb	uddctb	uudcstbb	udcssttb
N5¹	tbt	dtb	cst	ucb	cstb	dcttb	uudctbb	ucstb	udcsttb	uudccsstb
N6⁰	ttbb	ddtt	ctbb	utbb	ustb	udtb	udcsst	udsttb	udccsstb	uuddcstb

Reference

[1] <https://zenodo.org/records/18303155>